

Quantum Infidelity Codistillation for Fast and Accurate Distributed Quantum Machine Learning

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Abstract

This article aims to develop a scalable, accurate, and fast-converging method for knowledge transfer in Quantum Machine Learning (QML), which is essential for reducing QML model sizes to fit within a limited number of qubits. Quantum Knowledge Distillation (QKD) offers a promising approach that transfers knowledge from a pre-trained large teacher model to a smaller model. However, its dependency on the pre-trained large teacher model restricts its applicability to offline training scenarios and cases where a large number of qubits is already available. To address these limitations, we propose Quantum Infidelity Codistillation (QICD), inspired by co-distillation (CD) in classical machine learning and quantum state fidelity in QML. In QICD, following CD, each student learns from the ensemble knowledge of the other students, eliminating the need for a pre-trained teacher. However, the diversity among student models may lead to excessively high KL divergence, used in traditional CD for regularization by measuring knowledge differences, thus hindering training convergence. To resolve this, QICD employs quantum state infidelity as a bounded regularization measure, ensuring stable training. Using the Quantum Neural Tangent Kernel (Q-NTK) framework, we theoretically prove the asymptotic convergence of QICD and demonstrate that the convergence speed increases with the number of students. By numerical simulation on an image classification task, we show that QICD with four students achieves competitive accuracy compared to a baseline QKD using a pre-trained teacher model. QICD also achieves higher accuracy and faster convergence than a baseline Quantum Codistillation (QCD) that uses the KL divergence, highlighting the effectiveness of quantum infidelity regularization.

Fig. 1: Illustrative description of the behavior of (a) quantum knowledge distillation (QKD), (b) quantum codistillation (QCD), and (c) proposed: quantum infidelity codistillation (QICD).

Keywords: Quantum machine learning, distributed machine learning, knowledge distillation, infidelity, quantum neural tangent kernel

1 Introduction

Recent breakthroughs in computing hardware, particularly in quantum computing, have led to the emergence of quantum machine learning (QML) [1–3]. Unlike classical machine learning (ML), which operates at the bit level, QML operates at the qubit level, enabling parallel computation by leveraging both the superposition and entanglement properties of qubits. Consequently, in image classification tasks, QML has demonstrated advantages over classical ML, achieving faster convergence and higher accuracy at similar parameter scales [4, 5]. However, current noise intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) hardware faces significant challenges, including qubit instability and limited availability, leading to error-prone systems that constrain its practical application beyond theoretical research.

One approach to overcoming these limitations is quantum knowledge distillation (QKD) [6–8]. QKD utilizes a teacher model with a larger number of parameters and a student model with fewer parameters, transferring knowledge through an additional regularizer. This regularizer encourages the student model’s outputs—i.e., the measured observables—to align with those of the teacher model during training. While QKD achieves both parameter efficiency and high accuracy, it has the limitation that the teacher model must be pre-trained, restricting its applicability to offline training—an issue further exacerbated by the scarcity of large-scale quantum hardware.

To address this limitation, we introduce quantum codistillation (QCD) for the first time, drawing inspiration from codistillation (CD) in classical ML [9]. In QCD, we consider a scenario where multiple student models exist. Following the core concept of CD, QCD allows multiple student models to function similarly to a teacher model—when one student model is being trained, the averaged outputs of the other students serve as the soft target for knowledge transfer. This approach enables parallel online training of multiple student models without requiring a pre-trained quantum teacher model.

Motivated by prior works [10, 11], we extend QCD to develop quantum infidelity codistillation (QICD), incorporating an infidelity-based regularizer to further enhance accuracy and convergence speed. As illustrated in Fig. 1c, unlike QKD and QCD which perform regularization based on the post-measurement outputs, QICD performs knowledge transfer directly

at the level of the quantum state, prior to measurement. This design enables a fundamentally different form of interaction among students. Quantum state infidelity, inherently bounded between 0 and 1, quantifies the dissimilarity between quantum states and provides a stable and expressive regularization signal. In contrast to KL divergence, which can diverge when the outputs of multiple student models are highly diverse, infidelity remains well-behaved and robust even under such diversity. This makes it particularly suitable for multi-model codistillation in quantum settings, where state variation is expected.

Theoretically, we prove the convergence of QICD and demonstrate that its convergence speed increases with the number of student models using the quantum neural tangent kernel (Q-NTK) method. Experimentally, we validate that QICD outperforms both QKD and QCD in terms of accuracy and convergence speed. Specifically, compared to the student model baseline, QICD improves accuracy by 102.6% and 282.3% more than QKD and QCD, respectively. Additionally, when the distillation coefficient increases, QICD achieves up to a 511.8% greater accuracy improvement over QCD.

Contributions: The major contributions of this article are summarized as follows:

- To address the limitations of QKD, particularly its reliance on pre-trained teacher models and limited qubit availability, we propose QCD, where multiple student models collectively act as a teacher model. Furthermore, we introduce QICD, replacing the KL divergence regularizer in QCD with infidelity between quantum states, leading to improved accuracy and convergence speed.
- Using the Q-NTK framework, we theoretically prove the convergence of QICD and demonstrate that its convergence speed increases with the number of student models.
- We empirically validate that QICD outperforms both QKD and QCD in terms of accuracy and convergence speed. Additionally, we find that increasing the distillation coefficient further enhances the convergence speed of QICD.

Paper Organization: The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we review related works on knowledge transfer techniques in QML. Section 3 introduces the baseline models, outlines QCD, and presents our proposed QICD method. In Section 4, we analyze the convergence properties of QICD using the Q-NTK framework. Section 5 reports numerical experiments validating the effectiveness of QICD in comparison to baseline methods. We conclude with a discussion of implications and future directions in Section 6.

2 Related Works

2.1 Distilling Knowledge in Quantum ML

Numerous studies have been conducted to mitigate errors caused by resource limitations and qubit instability in quantum computing [6–8, 10]. One prominent approach is transfer learning, particularly through KD. The core idea of QKD is to transfer knowledge from a pre-trained quantum teacher model to train a quantum student model. However, this approach presents two major challenges:

- (i) QKD necessitates a quantum teacher model, which is difficult to implement with large-scale qubits due to hardware constraints.

- (ii) QKD fundamentally requires the teacher model to be pre-trained, making it better suited for offline training rather than online learning.

To address these limitations, several studies have proposed hybrid KD frameworks that integrate classical and quantum models—leveraging a classical teacher model to train a quantum student model [10, 11]. While this partially alleviates (i) by eliminating the need for a quantum teacher, (ii) remains unresolved as it still relies on a pre-trained teacher model. Given these challenges, our work explores a quantum-to-quantum transfer learning approach, drawing inspiration from CD in classical ML, where multiple student models replace the need for a teacher model.

Additionally, prior works primarily utilize KL divergence as the loss function for knowledge transfer between teacher and student models [10, 11]. Meanwhile, inspired by the Uhlmann’s fidelity function in quantum information theory [12], several studies have explored fidelity-based regularizers as inter-layer loss functions and have demonstrated that fidelity-based regularization improves training stability and accuracy [13, 14]. Motivated by these observations, we incorporate infidelity regularization into QCD, ultimately formulating QICD as our final design.

2.2 Neural Tangent Kernel

The NTK approach is extensively employed to demonstrate the convergence in both classical and quantum algorithms. In classical ML, several studies have established the convergence of KD and CD through NTK, especially under the assumption of infinite width. Similarly, in quantum ML, there exists convergence analyses of the Q-NTK — a quantum variant of NTK. This is particularly true in scenarios where the derivative of the weight remains constant (not time-varying) attributed to overparameterization. Key assumptions made in these analyses include a near-zero learning rate [15–18], infinite depth (i.e., number of unitary gates) [19], and infinite width (i.e., number of qubits) [20]. To obviate the assumption of infinite width or depth, some research endeavors have employed symmetric ansätze [21] or introduced additional regularization terms [22] for finite width or depth configurations, respectively.

3 Quantum Infidelity Codistillation

This section introduces the proposed quantum infidelity codistillation (QICD) algorithm, which operates on multiple quantum devices with student models. The algorithm is designed with distributed quantum machine learning in mind, where each student model resides on a separate small quantum device. This reflects practical scenarios in near-term quantum computing, where large, centralized quantum models are difficult to realize, but multiple small quantum processors can operate in parallel. QICD seeks to leverage such distributed computing resources efficiently by enabling collaborative training without the need for a pre-trained teacher model.

We use subscript i and superscript j to denote the data index and student model index, respectively. The task is multi-class classification on a dataset composed of input-label pairs $(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_i)$ ($i \in 1, 2, \dots, N_d$), where \mathbf{y}_i is one-hot encoded across C classes. For $j \in 1, 2, \dots, N_m$, each j -th student model is a quantum neural network (QNN), also called a parameterized quantum circuit (PQC), implemented on a Q -qubit system [23]. Here, a

PQC consists of a state encoder, a parameterized circuit, and a measurement layer, where the parameterized circuit, consisting of rotation or controlled-NOT (CNOT) gates, is represented by a unitary matrix U with the trainable parameters denoted by θ^j .

3.1 Standalone Training

The standalone training method optimizes each student individually. First, the j -th PQC encodes the input data using a state encoder and processes the quantum state as $|\phi_i^j\rangle := |\phi(\mathbf{x}_i, \theta^j)\rangle = U(\mathbf{x}_i, \theta^j)|\Phi_0\rangle$ through a parameterized circuit, where $|\Phi_0\rangle$ is the initial quantum state defined in Hilbert space. Then, the observables of the PQC for class c can be obtained by projecting $|\phi_i^j\rangle$ onto the z -axis, as in the following formula: $\langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i)\rangle = \langle \phi_i^j | \sigma_z^{(c)} | \phi_i^j \rangle$, where $\sigma_z^{(c)} = I^{\otimes c-1} \otimes \sigma_z \otimes I^{\otimes Q-c}$ is the Pauli- z operator for class c , in which \otimes is the Kronecker product operation and $\sigma_z = [1, 0; 0, -1]$. At this point, the parameters can be updated with a parameter-shift rule [24, 25] using the following objective function with local MSE loss, which corresponds to standalone training:

$$\min_{\{\theta^j\}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \sum_{c=1}^C (y_{i,c} - \langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i)\rangle)^2, \quad (1)$$

where $y_{i,c}$ denotes the c -th element of \mathbf{y}_i .

3.2 Quantum Codistillation

To enable mutual learning among students, we introduce quantum codistillation (QCD), inspired by codistillation in classical machine learning [9]. In QCD, when training a given student model, the outputs (i.e., observables) from the other student models are aggregated and used as soft targets. This allows each student to benefit from the ensemble knowledge of its peers, without requiring a pre-trained teacher model.

For student j and input \mathbf{x}_i , let the average observable output over the other student models be defined as:

$$\bar{O}_{i,c}^{-j} := \frac{1}{N_m - 1} \sum_{j' \neq j} \langle O_c^{j'}(\mathbf{x}_i)\rangle. \quad (2)$$

To compare model predictions, we transform the observables into a probability distribution using the softmax function. Let $P_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i)$ denote the full predicted class distribution of student model j for input \mathbf{x}_i , and let $P_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i)$ denote its c -th element, i.e., the predicted probability for class c . Similarly, let $\bar{P}^{-j}(\mathbf{x}_i)$ be the ensemble distribution derived from the average observables of the other students, and $\bar{P}_c^{-j}(\mathbf{x}_i)$ its c -th element:

$$P_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) = \frac{\exp(\langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i)\rangle)}{\sum_{c'=1}^C \exp(\langle O_{c'}^j(\mathbf{x}_i)\rangle)}, \quad \bar{P}_c^{-j}(\mathbf{x}_i) = \frac{\exp(\bar{O}_{i,c}^{-j})}{\sum_{c'=1}^C \exp(\bar{O}_{i,c'}^{-j})}. \quad (3)$$

We employ the Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence to measure the dissimilarity between these distributions. KL divergence is widely used in classical machine learning as a metric

to quantify the difference between a model’s predicted distribution and a target distribution, particularly in distillation tasks. Its formulation naturally captures information loss in approximating one distribution with another.

Then, the QCD training objective uses KL divergence between the student’s output distribution and the ensemble distribution, in addition to the supervised loss:

$$\min_{\{\theta^j\}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \left\{ \sum_{c=1}^C (y_{i,c} - \langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle)^2 + \lambda \text{KL}(\bar{P}^{-j}(\mathbf{x}_i) \parallel P^j(\mathbf{x}_i)) \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where λ controls the trade-off between supervised learning and codistillation. Note that KL divergence is not bounded from above and may diverge when model predictions are highly dissimilar, especially in early training.

3.3 Proposed: Quantum Infidelity Codistillation

Unlike QCD, which performs regularization at the output level (post-measurement observables), QICD leverages the full quantum state $|\phi_i^j\rangle$ before measurement. We introduce quantum state infidelity as the regularizer:

$$1 - F_i^{j,j'} := 1 - |\langle \phi_i^j | \phi_i^{j'} \rangle|, \quad (5)$$

where $F_i^{j,j'}$ is the fidelity between quantum states of student models j and j' on input \mathbf{x}_i . This regularizer is bounded between 0 (i.e., identical states) and 1 (i.e., orthogonal states), making it more stable than KL divergence in the presence of high output diversity among students.

Incorporating this into the training process, the objective function of QICD is formulated as:

$$\min_{\{\theta^j\}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \left\{ \sum_{c=1}^C (y_{i,c} - \langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{N_m - 1} \sum_{j' \neq j} (1 - F_i^{j,j'}) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

where λ is the distillation coefficient, controlling the contribution of the infidelity regularization term to balance knowledge transfer during training. Through this process, each j -th student model is trained once on the entire N_d dataset, completing a single epoch of QICD. The overall procedure of QICD is summarized in Algorithm 1.

To compute $F_i^{j,j'}$, QICD requires estimating the overlap between two quantum states, i.e., the fidelity between $|\phi_i^j\rangle$ and $|\phi_i^{j'}\rangle$. While full quantum state tomography could in principle recover this information, it is computationally expensive and impractical for large-qubit systems. Instead, practical techniques such as the *SWAP test* [26] and the *Schur collective measurement* [27] can be employed to directly estimate the overlap between quantum states without requiring full tomography. Furthermore, recent advances in *distributed overlap estimation* [28] provide a scalable implementation pathway for QICD in multi-device quantum setups, supporting its practical deployment in distributed quantum machine learning.

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode of QICD operation.

```
1: Input: MSE Loss function  $\psi(\mathbf{y}, \langle O(\mathbf{x}) \rangle)$ 
2: Input: Fidelity function  $F_i^{j,j'} := |\langle \phi_i^j | \phi_i^{j'} \rangle|$ 
3: Input: Number of data  $N_d$ 
4: Input: Number of student models  $N_m$ 
5: Input: Learning rate  $\eta$ 
6: Input: Distillation coefficient  $\lambda$ 
7: Output: Trained parameters  $\{\theta^j\}_{j=1}^{N_m}$ 
8: for  $N_d$  steps do
9:    $\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_i = \text{get\_train\_mnist\_example}()$ 
10:  for  $\theta^j$  in  $\text{model\_set}$  do
11:     $\theta^j = \theta^j - \eta \nabla_{\theta^j} \{\psi(\mathbf{y}_i, \langle O(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle)$ 
12:       $+ \frac{\lambda}{N_m - 1} \sum_{j' \neq j} (1 - F_i^{j,j'})\}$ 
13:  end for
14: end for
```

4 Convergence Analysis

This section presents a proof of convergence for the QICD described earlier. For ease of analysis, we assume θ^j to be separable for all j ($\theta^j = (\theta_0^j, \theta_1^j, \dots, \theta_{2^Q-1}^j)$) and rewrite the quantum state with coefficients as follows: $|\phi_i^j\rangle := \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} a_{i,q}^j |q\rangle = \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} a(\mathbf{x}_i, \theta_q^j) |q\rangle$. Then, (6) can be converted to the objective function below:

$$\min_{\{\theta^1\}, \dots, \{\theta^{N_m}\}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_m} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \left\{ \sum_{c=1}^C (y_{i,c} - \langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{N_m - 1} \sum_{j' \neq j} \left(1 - \left\| \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} a_{i,q}^j a_{i,q}^{j'} \right\| \right) \right\}, \quad (7)$$

where $\langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^Q}} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} w_{c,q} a_{i,q}^j \|k\| \in \mathbb{R}$, which is a generalized representation for measurement. For instance, a measurement with the Pauli-z operator on a qubit system with $Q = 1$ corresponds to the case where $w_{1,0} = \sqrt{2}$, $w_{1,1} = -\sqrt{2}$, and $k = 2$ in the aforementioned formula. For practical purposes, k is typically set to 2, but for the sake of analysis we have considered it to be 1, which remains a measurable value. It is also notable that (7) is a generalized objective function for all student models, which is a core concept for CD. Then, under the kernel regime, we can derive the following theorem:

Theorem 1 [Convergence of Quantum Infidelity Codistillation] *When the number Q of qubits is sufficiently large, the j -th student model's output of QICD converges exponentially to:*

$$\langle \mathbf{O}_c^j \rangle = \frac{1}{\alpha + \beta} \left(\alpha \mathbf{y}_c + \beta \frac{\sum_{j' \neq j} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^{j'} \rangle}{N_m - 1} \right), \quad (8)$$

where the rate of its convergence with respect to $q, q' \in [0, 2^Q - 1]$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{H}_q^1 [\gamma + \beta \delta_{q,q'}], \quad (9)$$

in which \mathbf{H}_q^1 is a quantum neural tangent kernel (Q-NTK), $\delta_{q,q'}$ is a Kronecker delta function, $\alpha = \frac{1}{2Q} \sum_{c=1}^C w_{c,q} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} w_{c,q}$, $\beta = \frac{\lambda(N_m-1)}{4}$, and $\gamma = \frac{\sum_{c=1}^C w_{c,q} w_{c,q'}}{2Q}$.

Sketch of Proof. First formulate the problem of minimizing the lower bound in (7) by introducing the inequality between infidelity and trace distance, followed by the triangle inequality. By making it time dynamical and differentiating it, a formula with Q-NTK can be obtained. Then, the lower bound convergence of QICD is proved under the kernel regime assumption. See A for more details. \square

From the result of Theorem 1, we observe that the final output of a QICD student model is a mixture of the ground-truth label \mathbf{y}_c and the average quantum states provided by multiple student models: $\frac{\sum_{j' \neq j} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^{j'} \rangle}{N_m-1}$. While Theorem 1 formulates a minimization problem for the lower bound of the QICD loss, its equality conditions require:

- (i) The student’s quantum states must be pure states, based on the Fuchs-van de Graaf inequality [29].
- (ii) The quantum states must lie on the same line through the center of the complex plane, derived from the triangular inequality.

In particular, for condition (ii), we can infer that if the students’ quantum states are correlated—such as when they are trained on independent and identically distributed (IID) input data—the equality condition can be satisfied. As a result, the outcomes of Theorem 1 may closely resemble those of the original optimization problem.

Remark 1 Defining the error of QICD as $e_c^1 := |\langle \mathbf{O}_c^1 \rangle - \mathbf{y}_c|$, the result from (8) yields:

$$e_c^1 = \left| \frac{\beta \cdot \left(\frac{\sum_{j' \neq 1} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^{j'} \rangle}{N_m-1} - \mathbf{y}_c \right)}{\alpha + \beta} \right|. \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, the result in (8) of Theorem 1 can be extended to define the error of QICD, as shown in (10) of Remark 1. Both the convergence speed and error of QICD, given in (9) and (10), respectively, are functions of γ and α , which are commonly dependent on β . A closer inspection reveals that increasing β improves the convergence speed, while the error remains largely unaffected, since β appears symmetrically in both the numerator and denominator of the error expression. Moreover, we observe that α is defined as the sum of γ over all q' , meaning that a higher γ leads to a larger α , which results in both faster convergence and lower error. However, since α is determined by measurements over a fixed number Q of qubits, it is effectively a constant in practice. Thus, the most effective way to accelerate convergence is by increasing β , which can be achieved by tuning the distillation coefficient λ or the number of student models N_m . In the following section, we empirically validate the effect of λ on both convergence speed and accuracy. Experimental analysis of the impact of N_m , which also contributes to increasing β , is left for future work.

Table 1: Accuracy comparison of QICD against comparators.

Models	Top-1 (%)	Mean (%)	Std (%)
Teacher model	72.71	71.99	1.08
Quantum Knowledge Distillation	60.66	58.60	2.19
Quantum Infidelity Distillation	60.76	57.18	2.89
Quantum Codistillation	58.19	56.16	1.51
Student Model	56.78	52.39	2.34

5 Numerical Experiment

Experimental Setup. The experiments in this section are conducted on a Linux-based server equipped with an 8-core, 16-thread Intel Xeon Silver 4215R CPU and $3\times$ Nvidia GeForce RTX 3090 GPUs. Python v3.9.0 and TorchQuantum v0.1.8 are used to implement the experiments [30].

We evaluate four models for comparison with QICD: (i) QKD with KL divergence using outputs from a pre-trained teacher QNN, (ii) QCD with KL divergence using outputs from other student QNNs, (iii) a standalone teacher QNN, and (iv) a standalone student QNN. All models perform 10-class classification on the MNIST dataset [31] using a cosine annealing scheduler.

Each QNN operates on a 4-qubit system. The quantum circuit architecture is composed of three components: a `StateEncoder` layer, a series of `U3CU3Layer0` layers, and a `PauliZ` measurement layer. The `StateEncoder` encodes classical input vectors into quantum states via amplitude encoding. Each `U3CU3Layer0` applies a U3 single-qubit gate followed by a controlled-U3 gate to each qubit. The measurement layer performs Pauli-Z measurement on all qubits. The teacher QNN uses 4 such `U3CU3` layers, while the student QNN uses only 1.

We use the Adam optimizer [32], KL divergence as the distillation loss for QKD and QCD, and infidelity for QICD. The distillation coefficient λ is set to 0.1. Other hyperparameters are: $N_m = 4$ student models, learning rate $\eta = 1e-3$, batch size = 1029, and temperature $T = 1$. Training is terminated if the loss does not improve for 50 consecutive iterations (i.e., batch updates).

Accuracy and Convergence Speed. Taking Figure 2a and Table 1 together, we first compare QICD to QKD, where QICD improves accuracy by 102.6% over the student model baseline, compared to QKD’s lower improvement. While QICD shows an increase in top-1 accuracy over QKD, it results in a 1.4% decrease in mean accuracy. Nevertheless, as previously mentioned, QKD relies on a pre-trained teacher model, which imposes memory overhead and limits scalability for online training.

When compared to QCD, QICD demonstrates a 282.3% greater accuracy improvement over the student model baseline, surpassing QCD in both top-1 and mean accuracy. This is consistent with [13, 14], which highlights that the bounded property of the infidelity regularizer enhances training stability and convergence speed. Additionally, unlike KL divergence, which is widely used in both classical and quantum contexts, infidelity is a quantum-specific metric inherently designed to measure the overlap between two quantum states. As a result, it better captures quantum correlations, coherence, and entanglement, ultimately leading to

Fig. 2: Comparison of (a) learning curves for QICD vs. QCD; (b) MSE training losses for QICD vs. QKD, QCD, teacher, and student model.

higher accuracy. When comparing the training losses of QICD and QCD in Figure 2b, we observe that the MSE loss of QICD converges faster and more stably, providing further evidence of the superiority of the infidelity regularizer.

Additionally, the standalone student model and teacher model represent the lower and upper bounds of performance for the remaining distillation techniques, respectively. Overall, the proposed QICD demonstrates superior performance in both accuracy and convergence speed, establishing itself as the most optimized approach for online knowledge distillation in quantum machine learning.

Impact of λ . Table 2 and Figure 3 illustrate the impact of the distillation coefficient λ on both accuracy and convergence speed. We observe that QICD consistently outperforms QCD in terms of top-1 and mean accuracy across all λ values, except at $\lambda = 0.4$, where QCD slightly surpasses QICD. In terms of convergence speed, QICD outperforms QCD across all λ values. As λ increases, QICD generally exhibits faster convergence, which aligns with our theoretical findings in Section 4. However, this comes at the cost of decreasing accuracy, representing a trade-off between training efficiency and performance. Notably, QICD achieves the highest top-1 accuracy at $\lambda = 0.5$ and the highest mean accuracy at $\lambda = 0.2$.

Based on these findings, we suggest a strategy for selecting λ : smaller values for high-accuracy tasks, and larger values for faster convergence scenarios. We also report precision, recall, and F1-score metrics for QICD and QCD across different λ values in Table 3, where QICD generally demonstrates stronger performance.

6 Conclusion

Toward achieving distributed online machine learning in the quantum domain, we revisited co-distillation in classical ML and introduced Quantum Infidelity Codistillation (QICD)—a quantum co-distillation framework based on infidelity. In QICD, (i) multiple student models exchange quantum states with one another, and (ii) regularization is performed by measuring the infidelity between the exchanged states. We provided a convergence proof of QICD using the quantum neural tangent kernel (Q-NTK) method and demonstrated that its convergence speed increases with the distillation coefficient. Experimentally, QICD achieves better or equivalent accuracy compared to QKD, despite not requiring a pre-trained teacher model.

Table 2: Accuracy of QICD vs. QCD w.r.t. λ .

λ	Models	Top-1(%)	Mean(%)	Std(%)
0.1	<i>QCD</i>	58.19	56.16	1.51
	<i>QICD</i>	60.76	57.19	2.89
0.2	<i>QCD</i>	58.29	56.20	2.49
	<i>QICD</i>	60.56	58.50	1.94
0.3	<i>QCD</i>	57.78	56.47	1.79
	<i>QICD</i>	59.94	57.78	1.68
0.4	<i>QCD</i>	57.36	54.62	2.22
	<i>QICD</i>	53.76	53.30	0.54
0.5	<i>QCD</i>	57.88	55.13	2.15
	<i>QICD</i>	62.41	57.09	6.42
1	<i>QCD</i>	58.08	55.44	1.41
	<i>QICD</i>	60.76	55.68	6.31

Fig. 3: Convergence speed (iterations until convergence) for QICD and QCD as a function of the distillation coefficient λ . Lower is faster.

Additionally, QICD consistently outperforms QCD in both accuracy and convergence speed, regardless of the distillation coefficient.

Although QICD operates at the quantum state level, whereas QKD and QCD operate on measurement observables, recent works suggest that quantum states with different dimensionalities (e.g., due to differing qubit widths) can still be compared or projected using techniques such as POVM/PVM conversion or subspace alignment [33]. Moreover, this opens the possibility for a hybrid distillation strategy—one that blends the state-level coordination of QICD with the observable-level compatibility of QCD—to enable communication across heterogeneous quantum systems. These directions offer promising opportunities to extend QICD to devices with varying widths, depths, and hybrid quantum-classical (HQC) setups. A detailed investigation of such generalized codistillation frameworks is left for future work.

Table 3: Summary of precision, recall, and F1-score for QICD and QCD across various λ values.

λ	QCD			QICD		
	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall
0.1	0.535	0.550	0.562	0.515	0.536	0.570
0.2	0.547	0.564	0.589	0.556	0.576	0.596
0.3	0.489	0.503	0.537	0.572	0.566	0.645
0.4	0.431	0.431	0.513	0.532	0.548	0.590
0.5	0.493	0.490	0.563	0.530	0.534	0.597
1.0	0.510	0.534	0.549	0.488	0.497	0.533

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Declarations

Not applicable

Appendix A Proof of Theorem 1

For tractability of the proof before going further, we first use the relation between infidelity and trace distance, denoted as $D_i^{j,j'}$, from [29, 34, 35]. Here, $D_i^{j,j'} \leq \sqrt{1 - F_i^{j,j'}}$ is accomplished where $D_i^{j,j'} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} \|a_{i,q}^j - a_{i,q}^{j'}\|$ and its equality holds when both quantum states $|\phi_i^j\rangle$ and $|\phi_i^{j'}\rangle$ are in the pure state.

Applying the above to (7), we can obtain a minimization problem for the lower bound of the QICD loss as follows:

$$\min_{\{\theta^1\}, \dots, \{\theta^{N_m}\}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_m} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \left\{ \sum_{c=1}^C (y_{i,c} - \langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4(N_m - 1)} \sum_{j' \neq j} \left(\sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} (\|a_{i,q}^j - a_{i,q}^{j'}\|) \right)^2 \right\}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

Since Q (also 2^Q) is large enough relative to N_m , we can update the lower bound minimization in (A1) to:

$$\min_{\{\theta^1\}, \dots, \{\theta^{N_m}\}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_m} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \left\{ \sum_{c=1}^C (y_{i,c} - \langle O_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4(N_m - 1)} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} \left(\sum_{j' \neq j} (\|a_{i,q}^j - a_{i,q}^{j'}\|) \right)^2 \right\}. \quad (\text{A2})$$

Also, the triangle inequality implies that $\|a_{i,q}^j - a_{i,q}^{j'}\| \geq \|a_{i,q}^j\| - \|a_{i,q}^{j'}\|$, where the equality condition is that $a_{i,q}^j$ and $a_{i,q}^{j'}$ lie on the same line through the origin in the complex plane,

yielding the following:

$$\min_{\{\boldsymbol{\theta}^1\}, \dots, \{\boldsymbol{\theta}^{N_m}\}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_m} \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} \left\{ \sum_{c=1}^C (y_{i,c} - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^j(\mathbf{x}_i) \rangle)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4(N_m - 1)} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} \left(\sum_{j' \neq j} (\|a_{i,q}^j\| - \|a_{i,q}^{j'}\|) \right)^2 \right\}. \quad (\text{A3})$$

Without loss of generality in (A3), we can focus on the first student model ($j = 1$) and vectorize it over the data points, simplifying it to the dynamics for gradient descent in [18], as shown below:

$$\min_{\theta_0^1(t), \dots, \theta_{2^Q-1}^1(t)} \sum_{c=1}^C (\mathbf{y}_c - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4(N_m - 1)} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} \left(\sum_{j' \neq 1} (\|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\| - \|\mathbf{a}_q^{j'}(t)\|) \right)^2, \quad (\text{A4})$$

where $\langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^Q}} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} w_{c,q} \|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\|$ with k of 1.

Deriving the continuous-time differential equation from (A4) is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \theta_q^1(t)}{\partial t} = \mathbf{L}_q^1(t) \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^Q}} \sum_{c=1}^C (w_{c,q} (\mathbf{y}_c - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle)) - \frac{\lambda}{4} ((N_m - 1) \|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\| - \sum_{j' \neq 1} \|\mathbf{a}_q^{j'}(t)\|) \right], \quad (\text{A5})$$

where $\mathbf{L}_q^1(t)$ consists of $\frac{d\|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\|}{d\theta_q^1(t)}$ as its i -th column.

Consequently,

$$\frac{\partial \|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\|}{\partial t} = \mathbf{H}_q^1(t) \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^Q}} \sum_{c=1}^C (w_{c,q} (\mathbf{y}_c - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle)) - \frac{\lambda}{4} ((N_m - 1) \|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\| - \sum_{j' \neq 1} \|\mathbf{a}_q^{j'}(t)\|) \right], \quad (\text{A6})$$

where $\mathbf{H}_q^1(t) = (\mathbf{L}_q^1(t))^T \mathbf{L}_q^1(t)$ referred to as the *quantum neural tangent kernel (Q-NTK)*.

We define $\langle \mathbf{O}_c^1 \rangle := \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle$, $\|\mathbf{a}_q^1\| := \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\|$ and $\boldsymbol{\delta}_c^1(t) := \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1 \rangle$, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_q^1(t) := \|\mathbf{a}_q^1(t)\| - \|\mathbf{a}_q^1\|$. Then, under the mild assumptions $\|\|\mathbf{a}_q^j\| - \frac{1}{N_m-1} \sum_{j' \neq j} \|\mathbf{a}_q^{j'}\|\| = \mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{2^Q})$ and $|\langle \mathbf{O}_c^j \rangle - \mathbf{y}_c| = \mathcal{O}(1) \forall j, c, q$ as in [36], (A6) becomes:

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\delta}_q^1(t)}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{H}_q^1(t) \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^Q}} \sum_{c=1}^C (w_{c,q} \boldsymbol{\delta}_c^1(t)) + \frac{\lambda(N_m - 1)}{4} \boldsymbol{\delta}_q^1(t) \right], \quad (\text{A7})$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\delta}_c^1(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^Q}} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} w_{c,q} \boldsymbol{\delta}_q^1(t). \quad (\text{A8})$$

Given a block vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}^1(t)$ with its q -th block being $\boldsymbol{\delta}_q^1(t)$, in (A7) and (A8), we have:

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}^1(t)}{\partial t} = -\bar{\mathbf{H}}^1(t) \boldsymbol{\eta}^1(t), \quad (\text{A9})$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{H}}^1(t)$ is a block vector whose q, q' block is $\mathbf{H}_q^1(t) \left[\frac{\sum_{c=1}^C w_{c,q} w_{c,q'}}{2^Q} + \frac{\lambda(N_m-1)}{4} \delta_{q,q'} \right]$ in which $\delta_{q,q'}$ is a Kronecker delta function. Under the kernel regime with lazy training via overparameterization ($\bar{\mathbf{H}}^1 = \bar{\mathbf{H}}^1(t) = \bar{\mathbf{H}}^1(0)$), we get:

$$\boldsymbol{\eta}^1(t) = e^{-\bar{\mathbf{H}}^1 t} \boldsymbol{\eta}^1(0), \quad (\text{A10})$$

showing the convergence of $\boldsymbol{\eta}^1(t)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Returning to (A6) to derive $\langle \mathbf{O}_c^1 \rangle = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle$, multiplying by $\frac{w_{c,q}}{\sqrt{2^Q}}$ on both sides and adding for all q leads to the following dynamics for $\langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle}{\partial t} &= \mathbf{H}_q^1(t) \left[\frac{1}{2^Q} \sum_{c=1}^C w_{c,q} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} w_{c,q} (\mathbf{y}_c - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\lambda(N_m-1)}{4} \left(\frac{\sum_{j' \neq 1} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^{j'}(t) \rangle}{N_m-1} - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1(t) \rangle \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A11})$$

If we take $t \rightarrow \infty$ under the kernel hypothesis ($\mathbf{H}_q^1 = \mathbf{H}_q^1(t) = \mathbf{H}_q^1(0)$), we have:

$$0 = \mathbf{H}_q^1 \left[\alpha (\mathbf{y}_c - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1 \rangle) + \beta \left(\frac{\sum_{j' \neq 1} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^{j'} \rangle}{N_m-1} - \langle \mathbf{O}_c^1 \rangle \right) \right], \quad (\text{A12})$$

$$\langle \mathbf{O}_c^1 \rangle = \frac{1}{\alpha + \beta} \left(\alpha \mathbf{y}_c + \beta \frac{\sum_{j' \neq 1} \langle \mathbf{O}_c^{j'} \rangle}{N_m-1} \right), \quad (\text{A13})$$

where $\alpha = \frac{1}{2^Q} \sum_{c=1}^C w_{c,q} \sum_{q=0}^{2^Q-1} w_{c,q}$ and $\beta = \frac{\lambda(N_m-1)}{4}$.

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